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Distribution of Edith's Copper *Tharsalea editha* in Canada

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ABSTRACT: Edith's Copper (*Tharsalea editha*) is a butterfly of conservation interest in Canada. Observations from the past 20 years are summarized and new locations are documented. This species now occurs annually in southeastern British Columbia; however, its range remains restricted.

INTRODUCTION

The first record of Edith's Copper (*Tharsalea editha*) in Canada was a specimen collected near High River, Alberta, by Thomas Baird in the early 1900s (Anweiler and Schmidt 2003). The species was not reported again until 2004 when Christian Schmidt found it south of Cranbrook in southeastern British Columbia (BC; Kondla 2007) in the Regional District of East Kootenay (RDEK). In 2006, Dean Nicholson recorded two more in the Cranbrook area (Kondla 2007; D. Nicholson, pers. comm.), and Norbert Kondla collected several from Yahk in the Regional District of Central Kootenay (RDCK; Kondla 2007).

The primary purpose of this summary is to provide updated status information for the evaluation of potential conservation priorities in Canada and the western provinces. This species is on the BC red list (considered to be endangered or threatened; BCCDC 2024), and on the arthropod candidate list for potential national assessment by the Committee on the Status of Endangered Wildlife in Canada (COSEWIC 2024). This article summarizes records of Edith's Copper in Canada since 2006.

METHODS

Personal observations of Edith's Copper are summarized. In addition, I contacted naturalists and lepidopterists with local knowledge in southeastern BC and checked online databases including iNaturalist, Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF), eButterfly, Butterflies and Moths of North America (BAMONA), BugGuide (Van Dyk 2024), and the Lepidopterists' Society's Season Summary on Symbiota Collections of Arthropods Network (SCAN) for additional records in Alberta and BC (see the references section for links to these resources).

RESULTS

Based on the queries listed above, there have been no reports of Edith's Copper in Alberta subsequent to the historical record from High River. All records summarized here are from BC (Fig. 1). There are two records for the RDEK since 2006, both by Dean Nicholson: one from the Kimberley area on August 5, 2012, and a probable individual northeast of Cranbrook on August 4, 2018 (D. Nicholson, pers. comm.; Table 1).

Nearly all recent records are from the Nelson area in the RDCK (Figs. 2-4; Table 1). The first report of Edith's Copper in the RDCK after 2006 was a male I discovered on July 13, 2013, along a powerline

right-of-way just north of Nelson, the Arndt property site, at approximately 600 m elevation. Two days later, I found at least one male, possibly up to three, along an old railway line south of town, the Salmo R site, at an elevation of about 900 m. This location was not visited in subsequent years; however, in 2017, Paul Prappas found Edith's Coppers at a nearby location, Apex wetlands, also approximately 900 m elevation. Observations of one to two individuals were made on August 15, 16, & 31. Up to 5 individuals were recorded at this site by Prappas in 2018 between August 1 and 21.

In 2019, I made targeted surveys for Edith's Copper at Apex wetlands. One transect, approximately one kilometre long, was followed six times from July 22 to September 3. One to four individuals were observed on each of these visits. Almost all coppers seen were males; one female was observed and photographed on July 22 near its likely host plant, *Rumex acetosella*. No oviposition behaviour was detected. The male seen on the last visit on September 3 was extremely worn but could still fly. This is the only September record for BC. This site, Apex wetlands, is the highest elevation of the Nelson locations and the copper's flight there is typically slightly later. Incidental observations in 2019 include one by Prappas at the Prappas property on July 8, and three by me at the Arndt property on July 3 (two males) and July 31 (one female). Both locations are at approximately 600 m elevation.

Edith's Copper was observed in 2020 at three of the previously known sites in Nelson and at a new location just west of town discovered by Prappas near Grohman Creek. Observations at the RDCK Nelson area sites for 2020 through 2024 are summarized in Table 1.

In 2022, I discovered a new location for Edith's Copper at Beaver Creek Provincial Park near Trail, in the Regional District of Kootenay Boundary (RDKB), while conducting butterfly surveys for the Kootenay Native Plant Society. Two coppers were observed on July 11 (Table 1). At this location in 2023, one to two coppers were observed on three dates from June 23 to Jul 14, and in 2024, I observed three to four coppers between June 28 and July 14. Butterfly surveys at Beaver Creek Provincial Park began in 2021 but the species was not detected that year.

In southeastern BC, Edith's Copper has been found in open, disturbed areas, often near water. All the sites that I personally have observed contain Sheep's Sorrel (*Rumex acetosella*), which is a likely host plant in BC. In addition to Sheep's Sorrel, native Willow Dock (*Rumex triangulivalvis*) is present at the Beaver Creek site (McKenzie and Machmer 2021). Edith's Copper has been observed nectaring on Oxeye Daisy (*Leucanthemum vulgare*), Common Yarrow (*Achillea millefolium*), aster (*Symphyotrichum* sp.), Tansy (*Tanacetum vulgare*), clover (*Trifolium* sp.), vetch (*Vicia* sp.), and possibly Wild Chives (*Allium schoenoprasum*) and Coreopsis (*Coreopsis tinctoria*).

The most consistent site for finding Edith's Copper from 2017 to 2021 was Apex wetlands south of Nelson. This is a former rail trail adjacent to a marshy area; during those years the trail was narrow and lined with a variety of native and invasive flowering plants, making for a productive site for observing butterflies. Up to seven Edith's Coppers could be observed in the one-kilometre section that was visited by Paul Prappas or me several times each summer. The trail was occasionally mowed in late summer. In late 2021 or early 2022 it was widened to more than 3 metres and surfaced with gravel. These changes affected much of the weedy margin that contained Sheep's Sorrel and potentially impacted the copper population there. After the habitat was modified, fewer visits were made for butterfly watching and monitoring, and fewer numbers of coppers were observed. One copper was seen at this location in 2022, one in 2023, and none in 2024. Because the low numbers co-occurred with a period of decreased effort, it's not possible to conclude definitively that the population is declining. If time allows, in 2025 I will attempt to determine whether the population at Apex wetlands persists.

CORRECTIONS TO CONSULTED DATABASES

Erroneous or misleading records of Edith's Copper in BC were found in two of the databases that were consulted. On eButterfly (see references for the link to this resource), two historical Edith's Checkerspot specimens from Vancouver Island are mistakenly named as Edith's Copper (checklists #76936 and #77022). Secondly, one of my Edith's Copper observations in the Lepidopterists' Society Season Summary SCAN database (Catalog #: LEPSOC_A_00076013) contains incorrect coordinates, resulting in the appearance of the copper's range extending significantly further north in BC than it actually has been found.

SUMMARY

There have been no reports of Edith's Copper in Alberta following a single record at High River more than a century ago. In BC, the species has been observed sporadically in the Cranbrook area (RDEK) since 2004; annually in the Nelson area (RDCK) since 2017; and each year since 2022 at a new location near Trail (RDKB). All records for BC are from the southeastern corner of the province. Its occurrence in Canada remains limited.

Fig. 1. Map of southeastern British Columbia, Canada, with names and boundaries of regional districts indicated in orange. Locations of all known Edith's Copper observations in BC are shown. Previously published records are in purple (see Kondla 2007; A: location of Schmidt's record from 2004; B: Nicholson's observations in 2006; and C: Kondla's records from 2006). Recent records (2012 to 2024) are in red; numbers correspond to those given in Table 1. (Base map courtesy of Ministry of Agriculture; green shading is Agricultural Land Reserve.)

Fig. 2. Edith's Copper, ventral. August 2, 2020. Apex wetlands. Photo by P. Prappas.

Fig. 3. Edith's Copper male, dorsal. July 8, 2019. Prappas property. Photo by P. Prappas.

Fig. 4. Edith's Copper female, dorsal. July 22, 2019. Apex wetlands. Photo by J.E. Arndt.

Site No.	Regional District	Nearest Town	Lat	Long	Elevation ^a	2012	2013	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	Flight dates summary
1	RDEK	Kimberley	49.671°	-115.930°	1000 m	Aug 05										Aug 05
2	RDEK	Cranbrook	49.581°	-115.671°	800 m				Aug 04							Aug 04
3	RDCK	Nelson – Arndt property	49.521°	-117.282°	600 m		Jul 13			Jul 03 – Jul 31	Jul 31	Jul 03 – Jul 23	Jul 30		Jul 03 – Jul 12	Jul 03 – Jul 31
4	RDCK	Nelson – Prappas property	49.502°	-117.274°	600 m					Jul 08	Jul 18	Jun 25 – Jul 23		Jul 01		Jun 25 -- Jul 23
5	RDCK	Nelson – Salmo R	49.389°	-117.218°	900 m		Jul 15									Jul 15
6	RDCK	Nelson – Apex wetlands	49.404°	-117.209°	900 m			Aug 15 – Aug 31	Aug 01 – Aug 21	Jul 22 – Sep 03	Jul 28 – Aug 24	Jul 01 – Aug 06	Aug 12	Jul 18		Jul 01 – Sep 03
7	RDCK	Nelson – Grohman Ck	49.501°	-117.377°	600 m						Jul 14					Jul 14
8	RDKB	Trail - Beaver Ck Provincial Park	49.059°	-117.613°	400 m								Jul 11	Jun 23 – Jul 14	Jun 28 – Jul 16	Jun 23 – Jul 16
^a Elevations rounded to nearest 100 m. See text for observer information.																

Table 1. Summary of locations and observation dates of Edith's Copper records in Canada since 2006.

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